

The multifaceted virulence of *Candida albicans*: A comprehensive review of pathogenic mechanisms"

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Virulence Factors of *Candida albicans*

Growth

C. albicans is able to survive and grow in markedly different environmental conditions. It can grow in the blood where the pH is around 7.4 and also in the vaginal mucosa where the pH is between 2.5 and 10. It has also been shown that *C. albicans* can grow in vitro at a wide range of temperatures between 5°C and 46°C (Hubbard et al., 1986; Odds, 1988). *C. albicans* grows optimally under aerobic conditions but it can also grow under anaerobic or micro-aerophilic conditions which are often associated with niches with increased CO₂ levels (Eklund and Jarmund, 1983; Hall et al., 2011). Under optimal conditions, it takes approximately an hour for *C. albicans* to double in cell number, making this fungus one of the most rapidly growing eukaryotes (Odds, 1988).

Morphology

Candida albicans can exist in three distinct phenotypic forms including the yeast form (dividing by budding), pseudo-hyphae, and true hyphae (in which elongated yeast cells remain attached after cytokinesis) (Figure 1.2). Yeast cells divide by budding, leading to the formation of buds which are generally smaller than the parent mother cell. Buds gradually increase in size and re-enter the cell cycle once they

exceed a critical minimal cell size. Pseudo-hyphae differ in so far as the buds become more or less elongated and cell divisions occur in a synchronizing manner with mother and daughter cells dividing together and remaining attached after cytokinesis (Kroin and Gow, 1995; Odds, 1988; Sudbery et al., 2004; Staib and Morschhauser, 2007). Hyphae have unconstructed evaginations that develop from yeast cells to form germ tubes—tubular structures that grow exclusively by apical extension. This induction of hypha formation from yeast cells is influenced by changes in ambient temperature, media of a neutral pH, elevated partial pressures of CO₂, nutrient deprivation, and the presence of serum proteins (Sudbery, 2011). Another morphological form in *C. albicans* is the elongated yeast cells called opaque form cells which are derived from normal yeast cells “white” colonies (Slutsky et al., 1985; Slutsky et al., 1987). The ability of *C. albicans* to switch from yeast to hyphal form is considered to be one of the most important virulence factors (Gow et al., 2002; Sudbery et al., 2004; Netea et al., 2008; Cheng et al., 2011). The damage to the host is caused by physical penetration by the hyphal cells, induction of inflammation, and secretion of enzymes that can degrade tissue components (Kumamoto and Vices, 2005; Gow and Hube, 2012). Many mutants have been created that are locked in the yeast form. Invariably these mutants, and those that are locked in the hyphal form, demonstrate virulence attenuation (Lo et al., 1997; Zheng et al., 2004). The Hgc1 cyclin is a major determinant of cell cycle regulation of morphogenesis in *C. albicans*. Deletion of HGC1 resulted in impaired hyphal development and low virulence in mouse models suggesting the importance of hyphal cells in virulence (Zheng et al., 2004). Interestingly, the deletion of HGC1 did not affect the expression of some hypha-related genes i.e., HWP1, HYR1, and ECE1 (Sharkey et al., 1999). Other genes which are involved in the regulation of hyphal

morphogenesis and virulence are TUP1, NRG1, RFG1, EFG1, and CPH1 (Braun and Johnson, 1997; Stoldt et al., 1997; Braun et al., 2001; Kadosh and Johnson, 2001; Khalaf and Zitomer, 2001; Liu, 2001; Murad et al., 2001). *C. albicans* cells lacking TUP1, NRG1, and RFG1 showed filamentous growth under non-hypha inducing conditions and are also virulence attenuated (Braun and Johnson, 1997; Lo et al., 1997; Kadosh and Johnson, 2001; Murad et al., 2001; Naglik et al., 2003). One of the first yeast-monomorphic mutants to be constructed by reverse genetics was the *efg1/cph1* double transcription factor mutant. This mutant is avirulent in mice (Lo et al., 1997). However, deletion of these two transcription factors affects the expression of multiple genes and the resulting avirulent phenotype may be due to pleiotropic changes to a wide number of virulence-associated genes. For example, the transcription factor Efg1 controls the expression of secreted aspartic protease genes (SAPs) which have roles in tissue degradation as well as GPI-anchored adhesins (Als3, Als5, Hwp1) which are important for attachment to host cells (Stoldt et al., 1997; Sharkey et al., 1999; Fu et al., 2002; Naglik et al., 2003; Sohn et al., 2003). Therefore, the ability of *C. albicans* to switch between yeast to hyphal form is important for the infection process but is associated with changes to the expression of a large suite of virulence-associated genes (Murad et al., 2001; Nantel et al., 2002; Walker et al., 2009). The white-opaque transition can also alter the expression of a large number of genes (Slutsky et al., 1985; Rikkerink et al., 1988) and thereby affect interaction with host cells and consequently its immune responses (Sasse et al., 2013).

Figure 1. 2 Morphogenesis in *C. albicans*

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